

DEVELOPMENT OF COMMUNICATIVE COMPETENCE AMONG FUTURE PRIMARY SCHOOL TEACHERS BASED ON TRAINING IN THE RUSSIAN LANGUAGE

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10418492>

ARTICLE INFO

Qabul qilindi: 10-December 2023 yil
Ma'qullandi: 15- December 2023 yil
Nashr qilindi: 21- December 2023 yil

KEY WORDS

*future primary school teachers,
Russian language, pedagogical
training, communicative
competence, technology.*

ABSTRACT

The article reveals the essence and possibilities of developing communicative competence among future primary school teachers through the organization of pedagogical training in the process of teaching the Russian language at a university.

The reform and development of domestic education, taking into account global trends, objectively determines the relevance of the competency-based approach. In recent years, in domestic psychological and pedagogical science, research has been actively conducted on the study of the concepts of "competence" and "competence" and the identification of various competencies for different types of activities. Competence is most often understood as an integral quality of a person, manifested in his general ability and readiness for activity, based on knowledge and experience, which are acquired in the process of learning and socialization and are focused on independent and successful participation in activity. The concept of "competence" is broader than the concepts of "knowledge", "ability", "skills", as it includes the orientation of the individual (motivation, value orientations, etc.), his ability to overcome stereotypes, sense problems, show insight, flexibility of thinking, character - independence, determination, strong-willed qualities.

Competence is also understood as a person's possession of the relevant competence, including his personal attitude towards it and the subject of activity. Communicative competence, along with others, is highlighted by researchers as one of the most significant and required in modern conditions. Researchers classify communicative competence as social due to the special nature of its functioning and significance in the development of both the individual and human society as a whole. It ensures the individual's readiness for self-realization and self-determination, is a means of creating and enriching a person's inner world, a condition for achieving harmony with oneself and the surrounding reality.

For us, communicative competence is of particular interest, since an important component of the professionalism and success of a future primary school teacher is the ability to effectively interact with other subjects. The psychological and pedagogical literature presents a wide range of interpretations of the concept of “communicative competence”. Let's consider some approaches to defining this concept. Communication in psychology is interpreted as a process of two-way exchange of information leading to mutual understanding. Communicative competence, according to L.V. Ryabova and S.I. Samygin, lies in the ability to establish and maintain the necessary contacts with other people. Effective communication is characterized by achieving mutual understanding between partners, a better understanding of the situation and the subject of communication (achieving greater certainty in understanding the situation helps resolve problems, ensures the achievement of goals with optimal use of resources). Communicative competence is considered as a system of internal resources necessary for building effective communication in a certain range of situations of interpersonal interaction [3]. E.V. Sidorenko includes three components in communicative competence: communicative ability, communicative knowledge, communicative skills [4]. Communication ability, according to E.V. Sidorenko, can be interpreted in two ways: as a person's natural talent in communication and as communicative productivity. Communicative abilities should include involuntary expressiveness, or the so-called “spontaneous coding ability”. It provides certain advantages in developing the ability to deliberately create certain signals. However, it is not associated with the ability to “read” other people's signals. Communicative knowledge is knowledge about what communication is, what its types, phases, patterns of development are. This is knowledge about what communication methods and techniques exist, what effect they have, what methods are effective in relation to different situations. This area includes knowledge about the degree of development of certain communication skills, and about which methods are effective for a particular person and which are ineffective. Communication skills - the ability to perceive and produce communicative signals: verbal, non-verbal and para-linguistic. According to G. Chanysheva, communicative competence includes verbal and non-verbal competence. Verbal competence is defined as the appropriateness of statements, taking into account the context and subtext of the statement, the absence of difficulties in written and oral speech, variability in the interpretation of information, good orientation in the field of evaluative stereotypes and patterns, multiple meanings of the concepts used, metaphorical speech. Competence in this case characterizes the subject of communication, his subjective qualities. Nonverbal competence includes paralinguistic and extralinguistic means of communication, in which preference is given to facial expressions, gestures, and appearance [5].

Summarizing what has been said, by communicative competence we will understand an education that is complex in structure and holistic in organization, ensuring the success of the main tasks of communication and self-realization of the individual.

Based on the analysis of psychological and pedagogical literature, we consider it possible to identify the following components of the communicative competence of the future primary school teacher:

- understanding the value and significance of communication for teaching activities, personal readiness to communicate;
- the ability to find verbal and non-verbal means and ways of formulating thoughts

adequate to interaction situations;

- knowledge about the means, methods, patterns, rules and norms of communication;
- ability to listen, hear and understand the interlocutor;
- skills of working on speech technique (breathing, voice, diction, etc.);
- skills of working in a group, in a team;
- the ability to clearly and convincingly present your ideas;
- possession of means of preventing and resolving conflicts in professional and life

situations, forecasting and assessing the consequences of conflict situations;

- emotional-volitional self-regulation as the ability to adequately regulate one's own behavior within the framework of communication norms in situations of social and professional interaction.

Communicative competence is formed only through the experience of one's own activities, therefore the educational environment of the university should be built in such a way that the student finds himself in situations conducive to its development. That is why the development of communicative competence in a future primary school teacher should occur in the course of specially organized training.

The main stages of work on developing the professional and pedagogical competencies of the future teacher in Russian language lessons include:

- preparation stage: psychodiagnostics of professional competencies;
- stage of awareness: informing students about identified problems, ways to overcome them and using exercises for self-disclosure;
- formation stage: conducting trainings for the development of professional competencies in classes in psychological and pedagogical disciplines;
- action stage: playing out pedagogical situations in practical classes and solving them independently by students in Russian language lessons.

For example, future primary school teachers developed a rapport-building technique that included the following steps:

1. Determine whether the attitude towards this person is positive.
2. Make eye contact, mentally convey to him the information that you see him and accept him.
3. Indicate a soft smile, relaxed posture, openness.
4. Reduce the distance in communication, if necessary, touch your partner.
5. Say that you are glad to see him, you enjoy this meeting.
6. Convey the necessary information.
7. Wish him well-being, a pleasant day, success.
8. Track your own feelings and thoughts that arose during the meeting, find positive and negative aspects in them.

Experience working with students shows that constructing dialogues and asking questions poses a certain difficulty for future primary school teachers. The lack of these skills leads to students formalizing communication, making it ineffective and unpersonalized. In this regard, we devote a significant place in the training sessions to exercises to develop the ability to ask closed, open, alternative and other types of questions. Thus, during the lesson, students played out situations in which the most frequently encountered questions in communication were used:

- open: What do you think about this? Which aspect is most important to you?;
- closed: Would it suit you if...? Do you expect that...?;
- questions expressing doubt (What would you say if...? Have you already thought about what...?);
- return questions (Do you really think that...? This is an extremely interesting question. We will return to it later), etc.

The technology of using clarifying questions was also developed, with the help of which one can effectively establish feedback with the speaker, reduce the likelihood of distortions and omissions of information to a minimum and thereby achieve the desired mutual understanding. During the lesson, students were asked a specific situation, in accordance with which future teachers had to formulate the purpose of the question and the question itself. Thus, communicative competence as a component of the preparation of a future teacher is necessary in modern educational conditions, ensures his awareness and preparedness for communication, and allows him to be included in the system of a wide variety of communication connections. Classes conducted using training exercises make it possible to more effectively develop in future primary school teachers not only a certain level of communicative competence, but also the need to demonstrate their own communicative techniques and tactics.

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